

Inventory of digital tools for routine (non-pandemic) care for chronic conditions during COVID-19

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The tables below present the digital health tool descriptions as they appeared in each document included in RAPIDE Deliverable 2.4, sorted by the **level of scale-up** for **each tracer condition**. Our analysis focused on **three tracer areas: cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and elective surgery**. When documents reported on more than one tracer condition, with or without additional health conditions, these were grouped under “multiple conditions.” To facilitate navigation, the descriptions are shown together with the scale-up level and the case country for each tracer condition category.

The level of detail varies considerably across documents, reflecting the diverse aims of the included sources. Only a limited number offered comprehensive descriptions of the digital tools implemented or scaled up, resulting in notable variability in the information provided. This compilation therefore serves as a supplementary resource to the main landscape analysis (Deliverable 2.4), offering extended descriptions of the digital tools referenced in the study. Definitions for scale-up levels and tracer conditions are available in the glossary of the main Deliverable 2.4 document.

Cardiovascular Diseases

Reference	Case country	Description of the digital tool	Level of scale-up: classification
(Omboni et al. 2021)	Italy	The web-based telehealth platform enables remote health monitoring, teleconsultations, and diagnostic testing in professional and home settings. Professional tests are uploaded via computer, while home data is collected through an Android™ app, with manual input or Bluetooth syncing. Data is securely transmitted, analyzed, and reviewed by physicians. Patients receive automated test reports, real-time feedback on critical health parameters, and medication reminders.	Large level of scale up
(Boriani et al. 2023)	Italy	A remote monitoring (RM) platform for cardiac implantable electronic devices (CIEDs) that enables secure, at-home device interrogation and follow-up. It transmits device status, battery and lead parameters, arrhythmic events, and alerts, ensuring continuous	Large level of scale up

		monitoring and early detection of malfunctions for pacemakers, ICD, and CRT patients during COVID-19	
(Hermans et al. 2020)	Multi-country	TeleCheck-AF is an ondemand mHealth solution for remote atrial fibrillation (AF) management that combines the FibriCheck® app (PPG-based) with a cloud-based dashboard. The “Check” component enables on-demand heart rate and rhythm monitoring via the app, while the “Tele” component provides structured teleconsultations through local clinical workflows. Together, they support comprehensive, real-time AF and risk factor management.	Large level of scale up
(Molinari et al. 2021)	Italy	Describes the telemedicine support from the telemedicine dispatch center, which includes remote telemedicine triage, pre-hospital ECG, ranging from its use for early diagnosis of CVD to rehabilitation, and chronic heart failure (standard pre-covid care model in Hospital networks in the study area)	Large level of scale up
(Magnocavallo et al. 2021)	Italy	This is a remote communicator device for patients that use cardiac implantable electronic devices (CIEDs). Patients were contacted for consent via email or phone call to receive the communicator at home received telephone training on the activation process and use of the communicator; additional phone contacts were made before or after the delivery of the communicator, if deemed necessary or if requested by the patient. The other group received it at a scheduled clinic visit and training was provided. All patients were asked to perform a manual transmission upon receipt of the communicator, in order to complete the activation of the system.	Large level of scale up
(Mickael, Lee, and Graham 2022)	Italy	Telehealth visits substituting for in-person visits	Large level of scale up
(Diemberger et al. 2021)	Italy	Medtronic cardiac implantable electronic devices (CIED) using patients implanted before the pandemic were included to monitor physical activity, heart failure diagnostics, and cardiac arrhythmias. Remote monitoring system for implantable cardiac devices, transmitting data every 3-6 months.	Large level of scale up
(Gawatko et al. 2021)	Multi-country	A CE-marked smartphone app (FibriCheck®) using photoplethysmography (PPG) for heart rate and rhythm monitoring before and during teleconsultations. Supported by Maastricht University Medical Centre+, it enables remote atrial fibrillation management, though lack of EHR integration remains a key barrier to long-term adoption	Medium level of scale up
(Molon et al. 2024)	Italy	A smartphone application used to collect patient-reported outcomes (PROs) from patients who underwent pulmonary vein isolation by cryoablation (PVI-C) to detect symptoms	Medium level of scale up

		related to AF and general health status, that is analyzed using the website and matched with all other patient data. Though not replacing the on-site regular visits, some sites performed remote visits (not described what medium was used)	
(Mazzone et al. 2020)	Italy	A telecardiology system within a hub-and-spoke model using web, telephone, secure email, and mobile tools for remote ECG exchange, rhythm monitoring, and teleconsultation. Integrated with electronic patient records and CIED platforms, it maintained electrophysiology services while minimizing infection risk	Medium level of scale up
(Ducceschi et al. 2022)	Italy	Implantable cardioverter-defibrillators (ICD) and Cardiac Resynchronization Therapy-defibrillators (CRT-D) are remote monitoring cardiac devices, allowing continuous surveillance and management of arrhythmias, for primary and secondary prevention of sudden cardiac death. The devices were implemented before the pandemic. Data comes from monitoring devices automatically every 1 to 2 weeks and is processed by dedicated professionals. These tools have been implanted before the pandemic with in-office visits for medical checkups according to the protocol of each hospital for the remote monitoring. During Covid-19, this was replaced by telephone consultation.	Medium level of scale up
(Kemps et al. 2020)	The Netherlands	Telerehabilitation programs using remote assessment and monitoring tools such as telephone, text messaging, emails, video consultations, web-based platforms, and applications.	Not applicable
(Cowie et al. 2022)	Multi-country	Various telemedicine platforms including phone, video calls, and apps remotely initiated to replace face-to-face consultation for heart failure management	Not applicable
(Brunetti et al. 2023)	Italy	Telemedicine and Telecardiology using ECG transmission, mobile telemedicine systems, wearable devices, smartphone apps, digital wearables, remote monitoring systems. Artificial intelligence and machine learning are used to analyze clinical data, improve diagnostics, and enhance patient monitoring.	Not applicable
(Pillon et al. 2024)	Multi-country	Various remote care and monitoring systems for remote diagnosis, monitoring, and therapy in vascular medicine, using encrypted video and conference call platforms, telemonitoring, and tele-expertise tools. Systems lacked interoperability standards, but emphasizes data privacy and secure communication, supporting care for patients with peripheral artery disease, venous insufficiency, Raynaud's phenomenon, and vascular ulcers	Not applicable
(Maines et al. 2020)	Italy	Telecardiology using phone evaluations and home monitoring devices for patients with cardiac implantable electronic devices (CIEDs)	Not scaled up

(Bossone et al. 2021)	Italy	A web-based system used to request for cardiac consultations, where the cardiologist at the hospital, based on the electronic charts information that includes test results, images, etc., categorizes patients into three clinical scenarios: hemodynamically stable, requiring a second cardiology opinion, and hemodynamically unstable. Those triaged to unstable category receives urgent bedside visits while their rest managed remotely, including video conferencing technology. The whole system, organization and functioning is supervised by a case manager nurse.	Not scaled up
(Piro et al. 2020)	Italy	RM system for cardiac implantable electronic devices (CIEDs) that provides data transmission from a CIED to a dedicated platform accessible by medical staff; delivered for patients without the RM during Covid-19 remotely or in-office after assessing several preset criteria	Not scaled up
(Salzano et al. 2020)	Italy	Telemedicine service (TMS) including phone calls (analog phones, smartphones) available 24/7, with the possibility of chat, video-conference services (with the most popular smartphone applications), and email, for heart failure patients, on a voluntary basis without scheduling from the healthcare providers since the patients were advised to use TMS.	Not scaled up
(Severino et al. 2022)	Italy	A telephone consultation for virtual management of Heart Failure outpatients to continue providing care during the restrictions.	Not scaled up
(van Schalkwijk et al. 2024)	The Netherlands	A telephone or online video (only 6 participants) consultation via Microsoft Teams with their cardiologists based on schedule	Not scaled up
(Biersteker et al. 2023)	The Netherlands	A set of mHealth devices including an activity tracker, blood pressure monitor, thermometer, weight scale, single-lead ECG monitor (Alivecor), and EASI-derived ECG monitor (CardioSecur) devices integrated with secured online dashboard for data access implemented to increase the detection rate of Post operative atrial fibrillation (POAF) and reduce unplanned ED visits after cardiac surgery. Patients were recruited and provided with The Box 2.0 before discharge, with technical support available throughout the study.	Not scaled up
(Brasca et al. 2022)	Italy	A remote monitoring feature embedded in cardiac implantable devices (CRT/ICD) by Medtronic, enabling continuous tracking of physical activity and clinical parameters in heart failure patients as part of ongoing device therapy	Not scaled up
(Giovannini et al. 2022)	Italy	Internet-based video conferencing platform used for synchronous and asynchronous rehabilitation sessions for frail elderly patients with chronic heart failure.	Not scaled up
(Mascioli et al. 2021)	Italy	A remote monitoring system for cardiac implantable electronic devices (ICDs and CRT-Ds) using wireless daily data transmission to a secure server. Managed via a portable patient	Not scaled up

		unit delivered remotely and online clinician portal, it enables continuous monitoring of cardiac status and patient safety during lockdown.	
(Mugnai et al. 2021)	Italy	A system for remote monitoring of CIEDs, allowing continuous follow-up and early detection of device malfunctions. Patients with CIED previously refusing device remote monitoring were contacted and strongly encouraged to accept. For patients who agreed, the device was dispatched and activated through a phone-mediated technical support system. Additionally, all devices without auto-thresholds (i.e., patients without PM-dependency) were exclusively checked through remote monitoring, and a mandatory attempt to solve all device alarms via phone communication, which was done in-person prior to the pandemic.	Not scaled up
(Tano et al. 2020)	Italy	A telephone-based telemonitoring system used by the ASST Cremona Heart Failure Clinic to manage chronic heart failure patients during the COVID-19 lockdown. Cardiologists and nurses conducted structured phone follow-ups to assess symptoms, vital signs, and therapy adherence, with some patients also enrolled in remote device monitoring programs for ICDs and pacemakers, ensuring continuity of care during service suspension.	Not scaled up
(Auener et al. 2023)	The Netherlands	A telemonitoring system for remote collection of physiological data (blood pressure, ECG, weight, oxygen saturation) via apps, tablets, and connected devices. Developed by Dutch hospitals and suppliers, it supports chronic heart failure, COPD, and hypertension management, though EHR integration remains limited due to interoperability challenges.	Not specified / unclear
(De Simone et al. 2020)	Italy	Remote monitoring tools are used to collect data with telemedicine services to optimize the clinical management of heart failure patients at home, improve their quality of life, reduce hospitalizations and emergency department access, and promote self-management. Patients with cardiac implantable electronic devices (CIEDs) were offered to use mobile devices (smartphone, tablets, etc.) and popular communication technologies (SMS, e-mail, video call, WhatsApp) for remote monitoring of health status. This changed the role of professionals in the organizational structure of the cardiology service provision.	Not specified / unclear
(Sebastiani and Anzivino 2022)	Italy	A range of digital and telecommunication tools—including mobile apps, smart wearables, AI systems, and EHR-linked platforms—used for remote monitoring and management of cardiovascular patients. Deployed by hospitals and regional health systems, these tools aimed to maintain continuity of care despite limited interoperability and coordination across platforms	Not specified / unclear

(Lindenberg 2022)	The Netherlands	A closed-system telemonitoring tool that uses a tablet with attached medical devices to automatically collect and transmit vital signs, detect abnormalities through built-in algorithms, send alerts to healthcare providers, and support direct patient-provider communication through video calling and messaging.	Not specified / unclear
(van der Vloed 2020)	The Netherlands	A remote heart-failure monitoring system that enables patients to record vital signs such as weight, blood pressure, and pulse through an app or online platform, allowing healthcare professionals to review the data, adjust treatment when needed, and provide follow-up without hospital visits. The tool also supports patient guidance and coaching by offering information, education on alarm symptoms, and self-management support for living with heart failure.	Not specified / unclear
(Peretto et al. 2020)	Italy	Developed by Wezen Technologies s.r.l., is a HTML5 web platform designed to organize multidisciplinary activities. Participants can attend meetings by using any kind of desktop, tablet or smartphone device. Medical reports and images are integrated in the platform through a middleware managing all HL7 and DICOM data flows. A bidirectional link connects the platform with the local hospital software, containing clinical data of both inpatients and outpatients visited at our Institution. Communication is allowed among medical specialists via video and audio teleconferencing. Televisits were performed by designated referral physicians (RPs) via hybrid models of care (including video/phone calls, secure email, or in-person visits for urgent cases).	Small level of scale up
(Tini et al. 2020)	Italy	Telemedical contact via telephone and email to monitor patients' conditions and assess urgency.	Small level

Diabetes

Reference	Case country	Description of the digital tool	Level of scale-up: classification
(Vonken et al. 2022)	The Netherlands	A web-based computer-tailored eHealth program designed to support self-management (adherence to lifestyle and medical recommendations using goal setting and tracking tools) in patients with type-2 diabetes. Integration with existing ICT systems was suggested to enhance compatibility.	Large level of scale up
(Danne et al. 2021)	Multi-country	CGM systems for continuous monitoring of glucose levels and telemedicine platforms for remote consultations and diabetes management. The challenges with integration with electronic medical record system and interoperability with other tools	Large level of scale up
(Perrone et al. 2024)	Italy	A virtual consultation platform (C4C Meeting) integrated with the electronic health record system to enable video visits and data exchange. Used by the Local Health Authority of Modena, it supports remote follow-up for stable type 1 diabetes patients, reducing in-person visits through secure data sharing and guided patient participation	Medium level of scale up
(Maietti et al. 2021)	Italy	TMTA services included teleconsulting, self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG) assessment, and tele-visiting (by email, video call, and/or telephone) effectively provide clinical support in several fields of application: observational/screening (e.g. retinopathy screening, foot ulcer assessment), personal health records sharing, and interventions (e.g. lifestyle interventions, therapy control and adjustment). These services have been present before the pandemic but their use has been intensified.	Medium level of scale up
(Natalicchio et al. 2022)	Italy	A mobile app used for digital coaching, allowing patients to register, provide personal and clinical records, and complete quality of life questionnaires. The aim was to provide educational and emotional support to adults with diabetes, improve diet, lifestyle, and management of diabetes.	Medium level of scale up
(Turlone et al. 2020)	Italy	A recommendation that includes remote glucose monitoring system using data-sharing apps to support virtual consultations between patients and diabetes specialists (telemedicine) and streamlined fasting glucose-based diagnosis in place of OGTT when necessary. Integrated with clinic software, it enables continuous management of gestational diabetes (GDM) and reduces the need for in-person visits during COVID-19	Not applicable
(Petrelli et al. 2020)	Italy	A continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion (CSII) system using insulin pumps managed through the Asur Marche Diabetes Center's "Sportello Amico" service, enabling remote	Not scaled up

		insulin delivery management and glycemic control for type 1 diabetes patients during lockdown	
(Fadini et al. 2021)	Italy	Remote consultations using email, phone calls, and other media to replace or supplement in-person visits.	Not scaled up
(Longo et al. 2020)	Italy	The CareLink Personal platform enables users to link their personal accounts to those of healthcare providers for sharing and remote reviewing of data from diabetes devices (The Medtronic MiniMed 670G, a hybrid closed loop (HCL) system that automatically modulates basal insulin infusion rates). Telemedicine was used for remote consultation with patients	Not scaled up
(Meloni et al. 2020)	Italy	Telemedicine services used for follow-up and management of patients with Diabetic Foot Ulcer (DFUs) following a new triaging approach that combined remote or in-person consultations based on severity and comorbidity. Those with less complicated and healed ulcers followed by phone consultations and ulceration pictures.	Not scaled up
(Scoccimarro et al. 2022)	Italy	Telemedicine support to patients with scheduled in-person appointments during Covid-19 to maintain glycemic control; no descriptions of detailed procedure and platform used	Not scaled up
(Boscari et al. 2021)	Italy	Clinicians access the glucose data captured by continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) or flash glucose monitoring (FGM) through various platforms, register all blood and instrumental exams sent by email from the patients, conduct a structured phone colloquium (Telemedicine Visit, TM), and send a report via email to the patients with changes in insulin dosage, if necessary.	Not scaled up
(Fratricelli, Di Nicola, and Vitacolonna 2023)	Italy	A platform used for creating a classroom-like environment for interaction with healthcare providers and patients, including multimedia content on healthy nutrition and active lifestyle. A one-to-one chat application was deployed whenever the web-based platform was not deemed user-friendly. The application targets overweight or obese subjects with T2D or impaired glucose regulation.	Not scaled up
(Munda et al. 2023)	Slovenia	Phone and email based consultations for follow-up visits and lifestyle education to ensure continuity of care and maintain good glycemic control	Not scaled up
(de Kreutzenberg 2022)	Italy	Discusses that telemedicine and remote continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) are the two health-related technologies most diffused during the pandemic, becoming essential tools in the management of diabetes	Not specified / unclear
(Van Grondelle et al. 2023)	Multi-country	A teleconsultation system using real-time video and audio communication to support remote diabetes management within primary care settings, ensuring continuity of care and reducing infection risk for people with type 2 diabetes during the pandemic	Not specified / unclear
(Wagner et al. 2022)	Multi-country	Telemedicine tools and diabetes technologies used for remote care and data monitoring	Not specified / unclear

(Forde et al. 2021)	Multi-country	In this survey with nurses, they reported large increase in virtual contact with people with diabetes (telephone, e-mail and video consultations, ranked as 1, 2, and 4 patient contact method during Covid-19 compared with Pre-Covid-19 period)	Not specified / unclear
(Giorgino et al. 2021)	Italy	Virtual clinics, online/phone consultations, and applications for patient education and telemedicine consultations.	Not specified / unclear
(Luzi et al. 2021)	Italy	A remote glucose monitoring system using Flash Glucose Monitoring (FGM) via LibreView platform used to track glycemic control and manage insulin dosing during lockdown	Not specified / unclear
(Choudhary et al. 2021)	Multi-country	An integration of telemonitoring system where healthcare provider is able to review glucose data remotely and evaluate glycemic control; mHealth where smartphone app collects and transmit data in real time; and telemedicine where provider and patient meet for consultation and decision making	Not specified / unclear
(Merino Torres et al. 2023)	Italy	A diabetes management ecosystem that supports telemedicine by allowing remote monitoring and management of blood glucose data. A Bluetooth-enabled glucose meter sends glucose monitoring data wirelessly to the OneTouch Reveal (OTR) mobile app on a patient's smartphone. The OTR professional application on the HCP's computer permits the healthcare provider (HCP) to access and view data within the patient's OTR mobile account, which also provides HCPs with a variety of clinical reports, including a patient summary report. In addition, the OTR Pro contains population management dashboards to help HCPs stratify and prioritize patients at higher risk. To communicate with the patients, HCP used telephone (mostly), email, text, video chat, or a mix of these mediums after receiving the glucose monitoring result.	Small level of scale up
(Parise et al. 2021)	Italy	Two virtual visits (video or telephone) were planned in the following sequence after securing verbal consent from patients: a telephone call was made during first contact where patients were informed about or instructed, if necessary, on how to download the data from continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) systems or a traditional meter into the cloud by using specific software, such as Clarity, Care Link, Eversense diabetes management system (DMS), Accu-Chek Connect DMS, and share the data through the cloud or email. Patients were invited to send recent lab results from other specialist care via email or mobile apps. The second virtual visit is decided based on various parameters, and all the information obtained during virtual visits uploaded to electronic medical files and the summary was shared via email.	Small level of scale up
(Sartore et al. 2023)	Italy	Telephone call-based telemedicine with service replacing in-person visits with additional email communication for patients with T2DM.	Small level of scale up

(Pelizzola 2020)	Italy	Several digital tools for remote monitoring and communication, including telemedicine interventions and electronic diabetic records to continue caring for patients with diabetes and managed in an integrated care approach with GPs and specialists. The importance of integrating to the digital health systems and glucose monitoring platforms was emphasized.	Small level of scale up
(Fresa et al. 2024)	Italy	An advanced hybrid closed-loop insulin delivery system (MiniMed™ 780G with Guardian™ 3 CGM) using the SmartGuard™ algorithm for automated basal and correction dosing. Integrated with the CareLink™ platform and app for remote data sharing and virtual training via Zoom, it supports glycemic control in women with type 1 diabetes during pregnancy and postpartum	Small level of scale up

Elective surgery

Reference	Case country	Description of the digital tool	Level of scale-up: classification
(Siragusa et al. 2023)	Italy	This includes several options used peri-operative and post-operative periods (remote triaging for emergencies, telematic follow up consultation, telemetric devices for home care, direct contact with the patients through private channels such as phone, text message, etc., online meeting with care providers)	Large level of scale up
(Velnar and Bosnjak 2022)	Slovenia	Telestroke, a national telemedicine network, facilitates remote neurological and neurosurgical referrals, triage, and consultations between peripheral hospitals and tertiary centers. It also supports e-consultations and phone-based outpatient follow-ups, ensuring continuity of neurosurgical care while reducing unnecessary hospital visits.	Large level of scale up
(Geerdink 2022)	The Netherlands	Virtual Fracture Care is a digital system that enables patients with simple, stable fractures to be discharged directly from the ED and managed at home through self-management tools, instructional videos, and remote guidance via an app or helpline	Large level of scale up
(Acciaro et al. 2021)	Italy	Telemedicine was used to evaluate the severity of the lesion for hand surgery and microsurgery between two facilities. Visual information was sent to Hub that allowed the decision to keep or postpone the transfer between the two centers.	Medium level of scale up
(Gallo et al. 2021)	Italy	Virtual consultations using video/phone call systems (not named), initiated remotely by hospitals or outpatient services to patients needing proctologic follow-up, triage, or post-op care	Not applicable

(Ciriaco et al. 2021)	Italy	Unspecified telemedicine platforms were used for patient follow ups and multidisciplinary meetings for initial and follow up consultations by a Tertiary University Hospital for Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) for pre- and post-operative care	Not applicable
(Di Bidino and Cicchetti 2020)	Italy	A telemedicine system enabling remote oncology consultations, follow-ups, and multidisciplinary coordination meetings, web-based triaging system. Implemented by Italian oncology centers, it ensured continuity of cancer care and treatment management during the pandemic while reducing in-person visits. Not integrated with the EHRs	Not scaled up
(Pignatti et al. 2020)	Italy	A remote triage and follow-up system using telephone, email, and messaging apps for patients to send lesion photos and communicate with clinicians. Applied in plastic surgery, it enabled remote evaluation and scheduling decisions to maintain essential care and reduce hospital visits during lockdown	Not scaled up
(Cammisa et al. 2024)	Italy	A dedicated software that makes it possible to perform video calls, fill out online questionnaires, and acquire X-rays remotely for total knee arthroplasty (TKA) post-operative patients. During the video call with the patients, 'remote' physical examination in addition to consultations made and the physician sends prescription for the X-ray via email. After the radiography, the documentation was acquired via a dedicated online software and second video consultation commences. Before subsequent follow up telephone and video calls, online questionnaires and privacy consent was secured. Final decision is arrived after accessing clinical and radiological data remotely.	Not scaled up
(Longo et al. 2021)	Italy	Telehealth systems for remote consultations and procedures (Patients were invited to fill out an online questionnaire and subjects at risk were automatically scheduled for a free telehealth consultation and/or an in-person visit)	Not scaled up
(Hsu et al. 2022)	Italy	Telemedicine platforms for virtual consultations, teaching, and training to mitigate the impacts of lockdown on the orthopedic patients disruptions of routine training, including the impact on psychological wellbeing	Not specified / unclear
(Aygün 2020)	The Netherlands	Physitrack is a rehabilitation application used for conditions such as hip and knee surgery recovery, offering exercise programs, educational content, secure chat and video calling with clinicians, patient-reported questionnaires, video-based exercise demonstrations, and a therapy-compliance tracking tool.	Not specified / unclear

Multiple conditions

More than one of the tracer conditions presented together with or without additional health conditions in the document.

Reference	Case country	Description of the digital tool	Level of scale-up: classification
('24/7 online medical service Telemedicine to be maintained post-COVID - The Malta Independent' 2020)	Malta	Slovenia's eHealth system supported non-COVID-19 care through tools such as electronic prescriptions (eRecept), electronic scheduling (eNaročanje), the Central Patient Data Registry (CRPP), and the zVEM patient portal.	Large level of scale up
(Testa et al. 2022)	Italy	A tele visit solution integrated into the Trentino healthcare system, providing remote healthcare services through a mobile app for patients and a web dashboard for healthcare staff. A mobile app for patients and a front-end web dashboard for the healthcare staff supporting clinical professionals for prescribing the Trec_Televisita app, scheduling tele visits, and checking patient's data; the functionalities of the patients' app included inserting files, images, chatting, viewing scheduled appointments, video calling, etc	Medium level of scale up
(Berti et al.)	Italy	The Sm@rtEven platform is a regional telemedicine system integrating telemonitoring tools (tablet gateway, pulse oximeter, blood pressure monitor, activity tracker, electronic scale) and the C4C-Meeting video system for televisits. It enables remote monitoring and follow-up of patients with chronic heart failure, diabetes, and COPD, transmitting data securely to multidisciplinary teams in Community Health Centers to support hybrid and continuous care in remote areas.	Medium level of scale up
(Wilman 2022)	The Netherlands	ConnectedCareCenter is a hospital-based telemonitoring platform where specialized nurses remotely monitor patients at home using Luscii's configurable system, which supports condition-specific measurement programs co-developed with medical specialists and aligned with clinical guidelines.	Medium level of scale up

(Omboni et al. 2022)	Multi-country	Telemedicine platforms for remote consultations and monitoring. AI-based tools for diagnosis and treatment. Mobile health apps for symptom checking and remote monitoring.	Not applicable
(Bhaskar et al. 2020)	Multi-country	A recommendation to include telehealth in the CVD and Diabetes patient care, including diagnosis and management. The professional consortium suggested a guideline to triage using phone and use available telemedicine platforms for remote patient consultations.	Not applicable
(Nataliia et al. 2021)	Multi-country	Applications selected via a national 'Express Contest' to provide remote home support for patients; a national telemedicine initiative in Italy using phone, video, and web-based platforms, along with digital screening and mapping tools, to deliver remote home support and monitoring. Coordinated by national and regional health authorities, it provided care continuity for COVID-19 and chronic patients through virtual consultations and remote tracking	Not applicable
(Petracca et al. 2020)	Italy	An integrated suite of telemedicine, digital triage, AI surveillance, and electronic prescription systems designed for remote care and public health management within national health systems, including chronic conditions.	Not applicable
(Ferorelli et al. 2020)	Italy	A broad telemedicine system using ICT for remote diagnostics, consultation, and monitoring, applied in chronic disease management, perinatal care, and emergencies. It is integrated with Electronic Health Records, enabling continuity of care between hospitals and primary care, and requires internet access and user training for effective use	Not applicable
(Kong, Riedewald, and Askari 2021)	The Netherlands	A web-based patient portal integrated with hospital electronic health records, allowing patients to access medical records, lab results, and communicate securely with clinicians. Used by Dutch hospitals, it supports remote care, self-management, and patient engagement during COVID-19	Not applicable
(Gabbrielli)	Italy	Digital tools include telemonitoring with connected sensors for continuous cardiovascular data tracking, telecontrol via real-time interactions and data sharing, televisita cardiologica for remote follow-ups, teleriabilitazione cardiologica combining home-based and in-person rehabilitation, and telerefertazione for remote diagnostic interpretation (e.g., ECG, Holter). All are integrated with the Fascicolo Sanitario Elettronico (FSE) and certified telemedicine platforms for secure, interoperable cardiovascular care	Not applicable
(Ministry of Health 2022)	Italy	Proactively monitoring solutions for patients with chronic heart conditions, such as vital signs e biometrics to detect a worsening CHF in advance or arrhythmias Digital tools include telemedicine platforms and digital home care technologies designed to support remote monitoring and management of chronic diseases and elderly patient	Not applicable

		care. The plan also funds digitalization of diagnostic and therapeutic equipment, enhancing remote service delivery and continuity of care within Italy's national health system	
(Simonetti 2024)	Italy	Not specifically named, but discussion around the application of various digital health tools	Not applicable
(Ministero Dell'Economia E. Delle Finanze 2020)	Italy	The Ricetta Elettronica (E-Prescription) system is a national digital tool enabling the remote issuance and delivery of prescriptions via email, SMS, app, or the national health portal. It allows patients and pharmacies to access and validate prescriptions electronically, ensuring safe medication access and continuity of care during and beyond COVID-19	Not applicable
(Ministero Dell'economia E Delle Finanze 2020)	Italy	The Ricetta Elettronica and Piani Terapeutici Elettronici (PTE) are national digital systems enabling the electronic issuance and management of therapeutic plans and specialist prescriptions. Integrated with SAC, SAR, AIFA, and the Electronic Health Record (FSE), they support remote access to long-term and high-cost therapies, ensuring continuity of treatment for chronic patients while reducing in-person visits during COVID-19.	Not applicable
(Ministero Della Salute 2022)	Italy	Digital tools covered include televisita (remote consultations), teleconsulto/teleconsulenza (clinician-to-clinician consultations), telemonitoraggio/telecontrollo (remote monitoring and control), and teleassistenza (remote support services). These tools are designed to integrate with national and regional digital health systems, meeting clinical, technological, and interoperability standards for chronic care delivery	Not applicable
(Ministro Della Salute 2022)	Italy	Tele-consultation between a patient and a health professional and between health professionals, tele-monitoring devices and tele-rehabilitation service	Not applicable
(Minister za Zdravje 2022)	Slovenia	Key digital tools include eKarton (national EHR), CRPP (central patient registry), and Telezdravje for teleconsultation, telemonitoring, and telerehabilitation. A national telehealth platform, central PACS, AI-based tools, and supporting systems like eRecept, eNapotnica, and mobile apps enable integrated, data-driven healthcare across Slovenia	Not applicable
(Ministero della Salute 2021)	Italy	A nationwide telemedicine system implemented under Italy's PNRR, integrating tele visits, telemonitoring, teleconsultations, and telerehabilitation across all regions. Expanded during COVID-19, it supports chronic, elderly, and post-acute patients via connected devices and wearables, ensuring remote care continuity and forming the foundation for Italy's national digital health platform.	Not applicable
(Francesco Gabbrielli)	Italy	A national telemedicine model by the Italian ISS combining video consultations, a mobile app, and home monitoring devices to manage chronic diseases like diabetes,	Not applicable

		cardiovascular conditions, and COPD. Supported by a cloud-based system, it ensured remote follow-up and continuity of care during COVID-19	
(Van Erkel et al. 2022)	The Netherlands	A telephone-based consultation for patients requiring follow-up care in various medical disciplines.	Not scaled up
(Nittari et al. 2022)	Multi-country	Platforms used for remote consultations, monitoring of chronic diseases, and COVID-19 triaging	Not specified / unclear
(Giansanti et al. 2022)	Italy	Telemedicine applications for diagnostic, monitoring, and rehabilitation, often based on mobile technology and wearable sensors. The applications were used to provide remote care for various medical conditions, including chronic diseases, diabetes, cardiology, oncology, neurology, and more	Not specified / unclear
(Monaco, Casteig Blanco, et al. 2021)	Multi-country	The stakeholder consultation stated the changes in care delivery for chronic conditions included digital health solutions, specially telemedicine platforms. However, the report has no specific tools analyzed and mainly focused on collaborative care solutions	Not specified / unclear
(Monaco, Palmer, et al. 2021)	Multi-country	Digital health tools include telemedicine, symptom monitoring tools, wearable devices, and digital communication platforms	Not specified / unclear
(van Hattem et al. 2021)	The Netherlands	Various tools for remote monitoring of patients' health parameters, enabling virtual consultations and continuous follow-up for patients with chronic conditions at the primary care and hospitals to minimize exposing them to the virus. The editorial discusses various telemonitoring systems, video consultation platforms, remote monitoring applications with emphasis on the need of integration with electronic health records (EHRs) and other digital health systems to provide comprehensive care.	Not specified / unclear
(Ágh et al. 2021)	Multi-country	Telehealth and digital prescribing tools were expanded to accommodate increased demand during the pandemic. Teleconsultation tools included phone, email, online chat, video consultations, and electronic health record (EHR) portals. Electronic prescription systems facilitated remote medication management (requesting chronic medication prescriptions was available via E-mail, Chat, Phone, VC, Web-based solutions, mobile app).	Not specified / unclear
(Behar et al. 2020)	Multi-country	Italy: no description of the telemedicine tools since the reporting is based on reviewing the telemedicine situation in the country. Tools include contact tracing apps, telemedicine platforms, mobile clinics, and remote monitoring devices.	Not specified / unclear

(Zaken 2023)	The Netherlands	E-consult, video consult, telemonitoring, and digital self-triage are complementary digital tools that enable written or real-time remote GP–patient communication, continuous home-based health data monitoring for chronic conditions, and automated online assessment of symptom urgency	Not specified / unclear
(Maaike et al. 2020)	The Netherlands	A set of digital care tools enabling patients to request e-consultations, conduct video calls with clinicians, be remotely monitored, and allow GPs to obtain specialist advice through teleconsultation.	Not specified / unclear
(Keij et al. 2024)	The Netherlands	A set of digital health tools enabling remote communication, home-based telemonitoring, secure access to personal health information through patient portals, and integration of data from multiple providers via a personal health environment.	Not specified / unclear
(Claudia 2021)	Malta	A telemedicine service offering telephone and video consultations that allows patients to receive medical advice remotely, with calls routed through a client support centre to GPs and relevant specialists for assessment and follow-up when needed	Not specified / unclear
(Verdnik Tajki, Virtic, and Dinevski 2021)	Slovenia	Telephone and email consultations for ongoing management and therapy renewal, eReceipt for electronic prescriptions, eNapotnica for referrals, CRPP for accessing patient data, ePosvet for secure provider communication, and mobile health apps for self-monitoring and disease management (e.g., diabetes, COPD, heart failure)	Not specified / unclear
(Cittadinanza)	Italy	Digital tools mentioned include telemedicine platforms and remote monitoring systems designed to support chronic disease management, enabling virtual consultations, health data transmission, and home-based follow-up between patients, caregivers, and healthcare professionals. The report refers mainly to tools such as tele visits, teleconsultations and telemonitoring patients with chronic with technological tools.	Not specified / unclear
(Patientenfed eratie)	The Netherlands	To monitor patients remotely, allowing patients with chronic conditions to check health indicators (such as blood pressure, heart rate, glucose, weight) from home, reducing the need for in person visits.	Not specified / unclear
(Bussemaker et al.)	The Netherlands	Multiple digital health tools	Not specified / unclear
(Matthew)	Malta	Telephonic consultation between healthcare providers and patients	Not specified / unclear

(Vassallo, Harney, and Abela 2024)	Malta	Telemedicine centre offering non-video-based patient provider consultations	Not specified / unclear
(Mifsud et al. 2023)	Malta	Electronic Patient Records (EPR), telephonic consultation used more often during the pandemic to provide remote care	Not specified / unclear
(Gesuete et al. 2023)	Italy	A smartphone app to monitor wounds healing in follow-up of postsurgical scars and diabetic ulcers. The surgeon can achieve, categorize, and precisely measure wounds remotely (width, length, circumference, area), thanks to a calibration system.	Small level of scale up
(van Aalten 2022)	The Netherlands	Thuismeten is a hospital-integrated telemonitoring app that allows patients with chronic conditions such as COPD and heart failure to record and transmit home-measured health data to healthcare providers, receive feedback and reminders, and support scalable routine digital care.	Small level of scale up
(van Elst 2022)	The Netherlands	A virtual ward, virtual fracture clinic, and Connected Care Center are digital care models that support home-based management of chronic conditions and simple fractures through remote monitoring, communication, and coordinated follow-up	Small level of scale up
(Cassar et al. 2021)	Malta	Funded by the state "With the aim to protect the hospital healthcare resources in the country whilst simultaneously safeguarding the health of COVID-19-infected patients, a telemedicine system led by experts was set up in Malta."	Small level of scale up
(Rant and Rudel 2021)	Slovenia	a multi-tiered telemedicine ecosystem enabling remote monitoring, digital communication, and clinical collaboration across Slovenia's health system	Varies
(Rant, Kosednar, and Stanimirovic 2023)	Slovenia	Key tools for chronic care include the zVEM patient portal for accessing prescriptions, referrals, and test results, the eAppointments system for scheduling visits, and zNET, a secure provider network supporting data exchange and continuity of care for chronic disease management	Varies
(Omboni 2020)	Italy	A combination of telemonitoring systems for chronic disease management. Telemonitoring was delivered via community pharmacies and family doctors to enhance remote care but faced poor interoperability with national EHR systems.	Not applicable
(Rant 2021)	Slovenia	Metadata for 15 telemedicine solutions in Slovenian healthcare were collected and grouped into three categories: telemonitoring solutions, remote provision of healthcare services that connect patients with healthcare professionals, and remote cooperation tools that enable healthcare professionals in different locations to collaborate on patient care	Not applicable
(Europe 2024)	Multi-country	Several digital tools targeting various user groups	Not applicable

(Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development 2023)	The Netherlands	Focus on telemedicine services broadly	Not applicable
(Fahy et al. 2021)	Multi-country	Several digital tools targeting various user groups	Not applicable
(Regional Committee for 2021)	Multi-country	Several digital tools targeting various user groups	Not applicable
(Bosa et al. 2022)	Italy	A set of digital health tools including teleconsultation platforms, e-prescription systems, and the Immuni Bluetooth contact tracing app, developed under the Italian Ministry of Health. These tools supported remote care, digital prescribing, and COVID-19 tracking, though interoperability with national health records remained limited	Not specified / unclear
(WHO Regional Office for Europe 2023)	Multi-country	Several digital tools targeting various user groups	Not specified / unclear

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